

MULTIFUNCTIONAL FIBERS AND COMPOSITES FROM (ALMOST) NOTHING

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ABSTRACT

At the dawn of the 21st century, nanotechnology was an emerging and rapidly growing area of research. With a critical dimension of less than 100 nm, nanomaterials often have extraordinary properties – for example carbon nanotubes have both high Young's modulus and strength. These novel nanomaterials are extremely small and difficult to see – literally – and could only be viewed and characterized using advanced technology such as electron microscopes. For years, researchers have tried to enhance the properties of fibers and composites by efficiently manipulating the microstructure using nanomaterials.

Advances in the field of nanotechnology, an improved understanding of the properties of the nanomaterials and the ability to control their structure enabled the technology to impart additional functionality to existing material systems. This led to the creation of multifunctional material systems by integration of a very little (almost nothing) amount of nanomaterials. For examples, less than 1% by weight of carbon nanotubes were added to composites to enable sensing functionality.

Because the addition of carbon nanotubes to matrix systems increased the viscosity and created challenges in the processing of composites, researchers tried to graft carbon nanotubes on advanced textiles such as carbon fiber using chemical vapour deposition (CVD). While CVD enabled uniform coating of fibers with carbon nanotubes, the process used temperatures in excess of 600°C. This often caused damage to the substrate fibers and made the process energy intensive, making it difficult to scale up. We have developed a novel electrophoretic deposition process, where chemically functionalized carbon nanotubes dispersed in an aqueous medium are deposited on a variety of different fibers enabling the creation of multifunctional fibers and composites. The mechanism of carbon nanotube film growth on non-conductive fibers is discussed along with applications as flexible pressure sensors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Increasingly, there is interest in developing light-weight multifunctional fabrics and composites by the integration of nanomaterials such as carbon nanotubes. These multiscale hybrid fabrics and composites with integrated nanomaterials leverage their remarkable properties due to the high surface-to-volume ratio. The combination of micro-sized fibers with nanoscale reinforcements enables unique opportunities to enhance the mechanical and physical properties of fibers and composites for multifunctional applications. Carbon nanotube coated multifunctional textiles have been used for a

variety of applications such as self-healing composites [1, 2], structural health monitoring and fatigue crack detection in steel [3, 4], thermoelectric and resistive heating composites [5, 6], damage sensing in adhesively bonded joints [7-9], flexible sensors for human motion detection [10-12] and improvement in mechanical properties [13]. The hybridization of carbon nanotubes has often been done using chemical vapour deposition (CVD) techniques where nanotubes can be grown *in situ* on the fibers and within the fiber bundles. But, the high temperatures and chemicals involved degrade the fibers. We have developed an electrophoretic deposition process (EPD) to deposit chemically functionalized carbon nanotubes using a water-based dispersion at room temperature.

The key working principle in EPD, is electrophoresis, the movement of charged particles in a dispersion/colloid under the influence of an electric field. Even though the application and practice of EPD can vary a lot, in its simplest form, an electric potential between two electrodes, cathode and anode, drives the charged particles in the dispersion towards the corresponding electrode and makes them precipitate on the electrode or substrate materials. For example, in the process we developed, an electric field is applied to chemically functionalized positively charged carbon nanotubes in an aqueous dispersion. Our EPD process is conducted at ambient temperatures and without the use of volatile solvents, making it environmentally friendly. Therefore, there exists an opportunity for scaling up EPD to a continuous roll-to-roll manufacturing process. The ability to control the key processing parameters such as the concentration of dispersion, deposition time, electrophoretic mobility of charged particles and electric field strength enables us to accurately control the deposition of carbon nanotubes.

An *et al.* [14] created an aqueous dispersion of carbon nanotubes and first deposited carbon nanotubes on conductive carbon fiber. The carbon fiber is used as an electrode due to its high electrical conductivity. Carbon nanotubes were also deposited on non-conductive fabrics such as glass fibers using EPD. [15] In this case, the glass fabric is in direct contact with an additional backing electrode which enables the deposition of the carbon nanotubes. In this research, we investigate the film growth mechanism of carbon nanotubes on non-conductive fabrics by using Astroquartz III, a type of glass fiber as model fabric. Carbon nanotubes are also deposited on non-woven aramid fabric. A proof-of-concept is shown of using the carbon nanotube coated aramid fabric as a pressure sensor for analysing human gait.

2 MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

2.1 Creating a stable dispersion of carbon nanotubes for electrophoretic deposition

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the functionalization of carbon nanotubes and the electrophoretic deposition process. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CM-95, Hanwha Nanotech, Korea) are first oxidized with ozone gas infusion and ultrasonication in the aqueous dispersion. Polyethyleneimine (PEI) (Mw 25000, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was added into the oxidized carbon nanotube dispersion to be grafted on the surface of the carbon nanotubes through the ultrasonication process. Glacial acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was utilized in order to adjust the dispersion to a pH of around 5.8. Amine groups on PEI polymers protonate under slightly acidic condition and make the carbon nanotubes positively charged particles and create a stable dispersion that can be used for the EPD process.

Figure 1: A schematic showing the functionalization of carbon nanotubes and the electrophoretic deposition process.

2.2 Manufacturing of flexible pressure sensors

A non-woven aramid veil (20601 50g/m²) was placed in direct contact with the stainless steel electrode connected to the negative terminal. Elastic bands were used to ensure continuous contact of the fabric with the electrode. Another stainless steel electrode separated by electrically insulative glass fiber composite spacers was used as the positive electrode. The assembly was immersed in the 1g/L PEI functionalized carbon nanotube dispersion. The electrophoretic deposition process was carried out using a DC field strength of 22 V/cm for 8 minutes following which the aramid fabric was dried in the oven at 120°C. The coated fabric which behaves as a piezoresistive pressure sensor is then laminated in 0.127 mm (5 mils) thick plastic sheets using a heat laminating machine (Saturn 95, Fellowes). Conductive silver paint (SPI Supplies) and conductive epoxy adhesive (Epoxyes, Etc.) is then used to attach lead wires to measure the electrical resistance. The data is collected on a custom built Arduino-based system using a voltage dividing circuit.

2.3 Scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy was conducted using an AURIGA 60 CrossbeamTM FIB-SEM with an acceleration voltage of 3 kV. The specimens were coated with a thin (~5 nm) conductive layer of Pd/Au to minimize sample charging using a vacuum sputter coater (Denton Desk IV, Denton Vacuum, LLC). For scanning Gallium ion images, the glass fabric was infused with epoxy resin EPON 862 using vacuum infusion. The composite was then potted in epoxy resin followed by polishing. After sputter coating, a Gallium ion beam was used for imaging which enables the differentiation of conductive and non-conductive areas.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Film formation mechanism using woven glass fabric as a model

Electrophoretic deposition can be used for hybridizing various kinds of non-conductive fabrics such as glass fiber [15], aramid and wool [16]. Woven, non-woven as well as knitted fabrics have been coated uniformly using the electrophoretic deposition process. From our previous research studies [14, 15], it is observed that carbon nanotubes functionalized with PEI uniformly coat all the fibers, not only on the surface but also within the bundles, and through the thickness of the fabric. The hypothesis on how the functionalized CNTs are destabilized in the dispersion and consolidated on the electrode and glass fiber to form a uniform CNT film was proposed and verified with the series of experiments.

Positively charged PEI functionalized carbon nanotubes are driven by the applied electric field to the cathode. The carbon nanotubes first deposit on the surface of the stainless steel which acts as a

cathode. The PEI-CNT film then grows over fibers of the glass fabric in direct contact with the electrode. Due to the electrically conductive nature of the PEI-CNT films, the film formed on the first layer of fibers acts as an extension of the electrode. As a result, the carbon nanotubes from the dispersion continue to deposit on the next set of fibers and so on until the entire fabric is coated through the thickness. Upon further deposition, the carbon nanotube film becomes thicker on the outermost surface of the fabric, the surface facing the positive electrode. [17]

Figure 2 shows the scanning gallium ion micrographs (SGIM) of cross-sections of glass fibers coated with carbon nanotubes after potting and polishing. Figures 2(a) and 2(b) are micrographs of the specimen coated for 1 minute and 10 minutes respectively, with all other processing conditions being the same, a field strength of 16.7 V/cm and carbon nanotube concentration of 1 g/L. One of the significant features of SGIM is the contrast between conductive and non-conductive materials. Generated secondary electrons are detected when gallium ions are radiated on the targeting surface. Conductive materials like CNT film where the gallium ions can freely move exhibit bright region whereas non-conductive materials such as glass fiber appear dark because deposited gallium ions are stationary on the material surface preventing the generation of the secondary electrons. [18] The bright circular rings around dark circles represent the carbon nanotube coating around the glass fibers. For both specimens in Figure 2, it is observed that every filament is uniformly coated with the PEI-CNT film, from the electrode side to the top surface. The key difference in the 1 minute and 10 minute specimen is the presence of a bright region representing a thick PEI-CNT film on the outermost surface of the fabric. As discussed earlier, once the PEI-CNT film grows around all the fibers through the thickness, the deposition continues to accumulate on the outermost surface.

Figure 2: Scanning gallium ion micrographs of glass fiber/CNT/epoxy composite specimens with a deposition time of (a) 1 minute and (b) 10 minutes of electrophoretic deposition. Bright regions are the conductive PEI-CNT film and the dark circles are glass fibers.

Figure 3 shows the scanning electron micrographs of glass fibers with PEI-CNT films deposited before infusing the epoxy matrix. Figure 3 (a) shows the fibers that were in contact with the cathode and Figure 3 (b) shows the fibers at the top surface the coated fabric. The fibers are cross-sectioned using a focused ion beam (FIB). The electric field strength and deposition time were 16.7 V/cm and 5 minutes, respectively. A PEI-CNT film of uniform thickness is observed around all the fibers in direct contact with the electrode. Bridging of PEI-CNT films is also observed between the individual fibers. The thickness of this film was in the range of 100-200 nm. In contrast, the thickness of the PEI-CNT film on the outermost surface is several microns thick. Additionally, the PEI-CNT film forms a continuous covering around all the fibers.

Figure 3: Electrophoretically deposited PEI-CNT film morphology on glass fabric after cross-sectioning on (a) the fibers in contact with the cathode and (b) the fibers at the outermost surface of the fabric.

3.2 Multifunctional application: flexible pressure sensors for gait analysis

The flexible pressure sensors created by electrophoretically depositing PEI functionalized carbon nanotube films on non-woven aramid veils were integrated with footwear to establish a proof-of-concept of using the sensors for gait analysis. Figure 4(a) shows the footwear integrated with two pressure sensors, in the hindfoot (near the heel) and in the forefoot region (near the toe). Figure 4(b) shows a typical ground reaction force in the Z-direction represented in terms of the percentage of body weight during a gait cycle. When walking on the flat ground, typically the heel first hits the ground followed by the midfoot and then the toe. The two peaks in the ‘m-shaped’ occur when the heel strikes and when the toe lifts off.

Figure 4: (a) A photograph of footwear with pressure sensors integrated and (b) a typical ground reaction force as a percentage of body weight for a gait cycle

When walking with the footwear instrumented with the pressure sensors, the electrical resistance of the sensors decreases due to the increase in contact points between the carbon nanotube coated aramid fibers. [19] Figure 5(a) and 5(b) shows the absolute magnitude of the resistance change when walking on flat ground and walking up the stairs respectively. For walking on the flat ground, as the heel first touches the ground, a change in resistance in the hindfoot sensor is observed. As the gait cycle progresses and body weight is transferred towards the front of the foot, the resistance change value decreases in the hindfoot sensor and increases in the forefoot sensor. The pressure sensors are able to capture the entire ‘m-shaped’ ground reaction force as seen by the superimposed image in Figure 5(a). When walking up the stairs, the entire foot lands at the same moment, causing a resistance

change in both the sensors. A significantly higher resistance change is observed for the sensor in the forefoot region.

Figure 5: Absolute magnitude of resistance change when walking (a) on the flat ground and (b) up the stairs. The shape of a typical ground reaction force on flat ground is superimposed to show the similarities.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Well dispersed and stable dispersion of carbon nanotubes was prepared by functionalizing with Ozone followed by grafting branched PEI polymer. Under slightly acidic conditions, protonated amine groups of the PEI render the carbon nanotubes electrophoretic mobility. Application of electric field using two pairing electrodes submerged in the dispersion drives the positively charged carbon nanotubes to the negative electrode. The film formation mechanism is investigated using a glass fabric which is then characterized using a scanning electron micrograph. A novel scanning gallium ion imaging technique is used imaging and focused ion beam is used to study the film thickness by cross-sectioning the fibers. It is observed that the carbon nanotubes first deposit on the negative electrode and start forming a film around the fibers in direct contact with the electrode. Since the carbon nanotubes are conductive, film around the fibers act as an extension of the electrode and film continues to grow until the entire thickness of the fabric is covered. A thick coating of the carbon nanotube film is observed on the outer surface of the fabric when EPD is continued for a longer time. Flexible pressure sensors are created by coating non-woven aramid veils with the EPD process and a proof-of-concept of using the sensors for gait analysis is shown.

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